

ACTUAL ISSUES OF INTEGRATION OF EDUCATIONAL SCIENCE WITH OTHER SCIENCES

Torayeva Sayyora Sattorovna

Senior teacher of National Center for Training pedagogues in New Methodology of
Surkhandarya region, Department "Methodology of Socio-Economic Sciences"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10577450>

Abstract. *In recent years, Uzbekistan has considered the implementation of large-scale reforms as a priority. As a bright result of this, it can be said based on the issues of quality education integration. The article covers the issues of integrative teaching of mother tongue and educational science in the context of time and space.*

Keywords: *integration, time and space, reform, quality education, new Uzbekistan, strategy, innovation, creativity, collaboration, communication.*

Enter. To prepare young students for social life in today's rapidly changing world based on the requirements of the times, to inculcate in them deep worldview, healthy faith, enlightenment, national and religious tolerance, social-civic, high moral qualities. formation remains urgent tasks.

Honorable President Sh.Mirziyoyev paid special attention to the education of the young generation from the first days when he began to build a new Uzbekistan and noted that this issue is a matter of life: "It is known that the education of the young generation has always been important and relevant. .But in the 21st century in which we live, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and death. In order for education to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to appear in this matter.[1]

His Holiness Navoi, who came to this world and did not acquire all the virtues and virtues created for man, i.e., did not infect, entered the bathroom and came out impure, in order to purify himself, he quoted the following verses.

Perfect your profession, you are the home of the world, don't die, don't be sad. I don't want to go through the world incompletely, it's necessary to come out of the bathroom unclean[3].

In our opinion, these immortal thoughts of Hazrat Navoiyi will be the answer to our following questions.

2. Methods. The "4 k" model has entered the updated educational system of Uzbekistan.

"1k" - Critical thinking (kritichiskoe mishlenie);

"2k" - creative thinking (kreativnoe mishlenie);

"3 k" - collaboration, that is, working with a team (kollektivnoe zaniyatie)

"4 k" - communicativeness - communication.

Students are asked the following questions:

1. What does a person benefit others with?
2. What is the purpose of human life?

We will connect the first verses quoted above by Hazrat Navoiyi with the science of education, focusing on integration education. We know that not only knowledge is imparted in education, but students are actively prepared for social life. That is, students are taught not to give opinions, but to think.

Where is the integration? The poet makes extensive comments about this. It encourages students to pay attention to the nature of the positive changes that are taking place and engage them not with empty talk, but with practical work. This is how he refers to a person who bears the name "human". That is, every person who comes into the world should be inculcated with the feelings of belonging to the homeland. First of all, it is necessary for our youth to learn in-depth knowledge in all aspects, to be a skilled master of their profession, to love their motherland, and to have qualities such as glorifying national traditions and values. Otherwise, as Hazrat Navoiy said, it is as if he entered the bathroom without washing and leaving without purification. This idea put forward by students is a clear example of critical thinking (in the example of "1k").

In order to engage students in creative thinking, the following question is asked. If you were to fall into the era of Alisher Navoiy, what would you bring from there (in the example of "2k"). As experts, we know that "Tarbiya" textbooks are based on the wise words of our grandfather, the enlightened writer Abdulla Avloni (1878-1934).

For example:

A child that can't be had by giving birth is a future disaster

If his body is trained, he will be able to do it

A scientist becomes the bane of a blacksmith if he gets an education

If his morals are broken, his son is a tyrant[2] .

(From the work of Turkish Gulistan or Akhlaq).

This is an example of "3k", whose students are directed to work with a team. Not all students have developed speaking skills. Even if some students know, they cannot express their opinion freely and independently. Working in a team creates an environment of healthy competition and allows students to speak freely.

It forms the ability of students to listen to each other, respect their opinions, and engage in dialogue based on healthy competition. This can be an example of "4k". That is, it can be an example of openness to communication.

Result: through the study of topics included in the subject of motherhood and education in middle and upper classes, students will acquire critical thinking, be able to cooperate in a team, follow responsibilities and obligations, develop physical and intellectual confidence, and take an active citizenship position. is taught to be able to occupy, to feel social existence and to enjoy it. As a result of teaching the above-mentioned "4k" model to the graduates in the classrooms, they will be able to cooperate with the work team and specialists, systematize the regular improvement of their knowledge and have an active citizenship position, be able to critically evaluate their actions, and be involved in the fate of the country. having high spiritual and moral qualities, as well as being able to promote them, they will have BKM and competencies.

Discussion: if the strict demand for education and its quality in general secondary schools is made a constant need by the school management, students and their parents, the teacher who regularly works on himself will be adequately encouraged. on the contrary, if an atmosphere of intolerance is formed towards teachers who do not pay attention to their own development, the teacher will have a desire to work on himself regularly, that is, to acquire knowledge and skills.

Conclusion: In conclusion, in Uzbekistan, where a legal, democratic and civil society is being built, the quality integration of native and educational sciences is one of the bold steps to create a modern and rational system in the field of education and training, to bring the education system equal to world standards and in the world serves to train competitive personnel.

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